

INDEX NUMBER.....STUDENT'S SIGNATURE.....

HFNMTC- BEREKUM

END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION: 28TH SEPTEMBER, 2021

(RM17) RMD 225 COMMUNITY MIDWIFERY

TIME ALLOWED: 1 ½ HOUR

OBJECTIVES

INSTRUCTIONS

- *Answer all questions.*
- *Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet.*
- *Each question carries 20 marks.*
- *Read the questions carefully and provide only the relevant answers.*

Note that any number of points provide beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any mark.

QUESTION ONE

- a. Differentiate between skilled birth attendant and birth attendant - 1 MARK
- b. What is delay in health - 3 MARKS
- c. State and explain four (4) responsibility of a midwife regarding obstetric emergency care 8 MARKS
- d. In a tabular form state 4 differences between examination of a puerperal woman who visited your facility for 1st (8 days after delivery) and 2nd post natal visits as well as that of the baby - 8 MARKS

QUESTION TWO

- a. What constitutes an enabling environment for home delivery? - 5MARKS
- b. Nyamebkyere is a small village. Inhabitants are recording high levels of diseases, illness, injuries and disabilities. What might be the cause - 7MARKS
- c. In a town of 36000 people, there are 120 live births, and 60 infants 'death. What is the fertility rate? (show work) - 4 MARKS
- d. The effect of migration on population change can be sudden. Simply explain factors that influence population growth - 4 MARKS

QUESTION THREE

- a. Explain factors you would consider when selecting client for home delivery - 7 MARKS
- b. State the pillars of safe motherhood - 3 MARKS
- c. Explain cold chain system in Ghana - 10 MARKS

MS. MARTHA KYEREMAA

INDEX NUMBER.....

HOLY FNMTC-BEREKUM

END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION- MAY 2019

RM15: COMMUNITY MIDWIFERY 1: RMD 225

TIME ALLOWED: 2HOURS

ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS:

- Answer all questions
- Each question must be answered in a separate booklet
- Each question carries 20marks
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers
- Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any mark.

QUESTION ONE

Obstetric emergency care is an immediate care given to women to prevent complication or death

- Mention 4 disciplines (categories) with 4 conditions each under obstetric emergency - 10marks
- Give the 2 other names of natural family planning and Mention the 4 main methods with an example where applicable - 5 marks
- Mention the five (5) components of safe Motherhood - 5 marks

QUESTION TWO

- Mention the three (3) determinate of population growth. - 3 marks
- State the types of migration. - 2 marks
- Enumerate eight (8) effect of population growth in the Country. - 8 marks
- There are seven (7) Statistical observations made by researches under population growth, outline them. - 7 marks

QUESTION THREE

- State and explain the two (2) main types of immunity to your colleague who missed the class that day - 9 marks

In a town, Domeabra with the population of 200,000 people 720 live births occurred among 36000 women and, there was 60 infants death.

- Calculate fertility rate show work - 4 marks
- Mention 4 push and 4 pull factors as in migration. - 4marks
- In your own words define safe motherhood - 3 marks

QUESTION FOUR

- Mention eight (8) advantages of home visit. - 8 marks
- Mention six (6) disadvantages of home visit. - 6marks
- Give four (4) Delays in Emergency Obstetric Care(EMOC) - 4 marks
- Give two levels of care in EMOC - 2 marks

HFNMTC – BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION – MAY, 2019
PBM II: COMMUNITY MIDWIFERY 1: RMP 126
TIME ALLOWED: 2HOURS
ESSAY

Instructions

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet.
- Each question carries 20 marks.
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers.

Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any marks.

QUESTION ONE

- | | |
|--|---------|
| a. In your own words define safe motherhood | 1 mark |
| b. State six(6) components of safe motherhood | 6 marks |
| c. State four (4) objectives of safe motherhood | 4 marks |
| d. List six (6) puerperal complication to the mother and six (6) complication to the baby | 6 marks |
| e. Withdrawal is one of the natural family planning methods mention the other 3 | 3 marks |

QUESTION TWO

- | | |
|---|---------|
| a. State and explain the two (2) main types of immunity to your colleague who missed the class last time | 6 marks |
| b. List six (6) equipment used in maintaining vaccine potency in the cold chain | 3 marks |
| c. State the major factors in maintaining cold chain | 3 marks |
| d. Outline four (4) responsibilities each of TBA and CHO | 4 marks |
| e. State four (4) most important things you will look for when examine a baby four (4) days old | 4 marks |

QUESTION THREE

- | | |
|--|---------|
| a. In your own words define migration and state the types | 3 marks |
| b. Enumerate eight (8) effects of population growth in the community | 8 marks |
| c. There are seven (7) statistical observations made by researches under population growth outline them | 7 marks |
| d. Explain in simple terms skill birth attendant | 2 marks |

QUESTION FOUR

Asempanaye village has a population of 220,000 people, 12,000 are WIFA with 66 live births occurred in the year 2000, and there was 6 infants deaths

- | | |
|--|----------|
| a. Calculate fertility rate and infant mortality rate (show work) | 6 marks |
| b. Mrs. Tweneboah has met the requirement for establishing her maternity home. Give ten (10) things that made her to meet the requirement with reason | 10 marks |
| c. In a tabular form give four (4) each, push and pull factors as in migration | 4 marks |

HFNMTC- BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION
RGN20. COMMUNITY BASED REHABILITATION.
TIME ALLOWED: 1 ½ HRS
ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS

- Answer all questions
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet
- Each question carries 20 marks.
- Read the questions carefully and provide only the relevant answers
- Note that any number of points provide beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will attract any mark

QUESTION ONE

- a. Outline three (3) roles each of the following rehabilitation team members
- i. Physiotherapist
 - ii. Social worker
 - iii. Psychologist
- 9 marks
- b. State the **three (3)** principles of counseling - 3marks
- c. List the **two (2)** goals of counseling - 2marks
- d. Enumerate **eight (8)** duties of a counsellor to the disable - 4marks
- e. Enumerate **two (2)** functions of communication boards to the child - 2marks

QUESTION TWO

Tawiah, a 20 year old disable person with mobility impairment is living in your community and will need some form of rehabilitation.

- a. Mention and explain five roles of the nurse in the rehabilitation of Tawiah? - 10 marks
- b. Give **four (4)** benefits of rehabilitation to Tawiah. - 4 marks
- c. State the three (3) types of rehabilitation - 3marks
- d. Mention three (3) tools that will be used in rehabilitating Tawiah - 3marks

QUESTION THREE

The incidence of disability has always been on the increasing trend and about 60% of disabilities could have been prevented.

- a. As a nurse, how will you prevent disabilities under the following in the community?
- i. Primordial
 - ii. Primary
 - iii. Secondary
 - iv. Tertiary
- 8 marks
- b. Mr. Kontor, a 50 year old man with visual impairment is living in your community and will need some empowerment to cope with his disabilities. State and explain **five (5)** ways by which you can empower him. - 10 marks
- c. State **four(4)** rehabilitation tools that you will recommend for Mr. Kontor - 2marks

WHO Modified Partograph

Registration No. _____ Name (Last, First) _____ Age _____
 Date _____ Parity/Gravida _____ / _____ LMP _____ EDD _____ Gestation (wks) _____
 ROM (Time, Date) _____ / _____ Labour Durable (Hrs) _____ Facility/Clinic Name _____

FETAL
HEART
RATE

LIQUOR
MOULDING

CERVIX
(CM)

Plot X

DESCENT

HOURS
TIME

CONTRACTIONS
PER 10 MINS

Oxytocin U/L
Drops / Minute

DRUGS
&
IV FLUIDS

BLOOD
PRESSURE
&
PULSE

TEMPERATURE

LABOUR NOTES

Please circle or write responses.

DELIVERY

DATE: _____ TIME: _____ METHOD: Spontaneous / Vacuum Extraction / C/S / Other
 PERINEUM: Intact / Episiotomy / Laceration
 ANESTHESIA: None / Local / General

THIRD STAGE

Active Management: Yes / No Medication: Time _____ Type / Dose _____

PLACENTA: Time: _____ Complete / Incomplete

BLOOD LOSS AMOUNT: Small (less than 250 cc)
 Moderate (250-499 cc)
 Large (more than 500 cc)
 Significant for mother

BABY

Weight: _____

Sex: Male / Female

Baby Position: Vertex / Breech / Other

APGAR

Time	Color	Breath	Heart	Tone	Reflex	TOTAL
1 min						
5 min						

COMPLICATIONS OF MOTHER / BABY: None / Other: _____

FOURTH STAGE MONITORING

Frequency	Time	B/P	Pulse	Fundus	Bleeding	Bladder
Every 15 minutes first 2 hours						
Every 30 minutes for 1 hour						

Birth Attendant _____

Date _____

NMTC – BEREKUM
END OF FIRST SEMESTER – DECEMBER, 2015
COMMUNITY MIDWIFERY (RM 11)
TIME ALLOWED: 2HRS.
ESSAY

Instructions:

- Answer all questions
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet
- Each question carries 20marks
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers

Not that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any marks.

Question One

- a. As a community midwife, list four (4) types of health facilities or service providers you are likely to work with in your operational area. 4marks.
- b. Define the term Cold Chain, with systematically and diagrammatically flow of cold chain. 11marks
- c. State and explain the uses of Age-structure in a given population. 5marks

Question Two

Home visiting offers the nurse/midwife a wider scope of services since she is able to use what the clients have to demonstrate to them.

- a. Explain six (6) points on Planning and Preparation for Home Visiting. - 8marks
- b. Define the term population. - 2 marks
- c. The target for Ghana Immunization Programme on Vaccine preventable diseases in children from 0-5 years has been 80%. Explain five (5) immunization strategies in Ghana. - 10marks

Question Three

- a. Elaborate Tetanus-Toxoid immunization schedule for Women in Fertility Age. - 5marks
- b. The legal aspect of nursing is an integral part of everyday activities in general health, mental health and midwifery practice. Explain any six (6) behaviors or attitudes of a nurse that may result in a lawsuit. - 7marks
- c. State eight (8) things to remember in maintaining vaccines' potency. - 8marks

INDEX NUMBER.....

HFNMTC – BEREKUM/ST. MARY'S CAMPUS - DROBO

END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION - MAY 2018

RM 14 RMD COMMUNITY MIDWIFERY

TIME ALLOWED: 2 HRS

ESSAY

Instructions:

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate booklet
- Each question carries 20marks
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers
- Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any mark.

Question One

One of the primary areas of interest to demographers is analysis of human fertility. They aim to evaluate the factors that can be ascribed to fertility change

- a. Mention 10 of these factors - 10 marks
- b. What are the effects of high population - 8marks
- c. As a community midwife, which people are you likely to work with at the sub district level (not less than 4) - 2marks

Question Two

- a. There is an ongoing campaign educating people on some of the risk people put themselves through in order to get access to developed countries. However the youth are playing adamant to theses education. What factors might contribute to this high movement - 7marks
- b. Nyamebekyere is a small village. Inhabitants are recording high levels of diseases, illness, injuries and disabilities. What might be the cause - 7marks
- c. What are the components of safe motherhood - 6marks

Question Three

- a. Explain five (5) factors you would consider when selecting client for home delivery - 10 marks
- b. Mrs. Donsa had Spontaneous Vagina Delivery (SVD) 72 hours ago with a baby boy and she is at home. State five (5) things you will look for each on the mother and the baby as a community midwife - 10 marks

Question Four.

- a. State the key elements of Cold Chain System in Ghana - 3 marks
- b. Enumerate seven (7) ways to plan and prepare for home visit - 7 marks
- c. State seven (7) ways to maintain vaccine potency - 7 marks
- d. In about three (3) sentences explain safe motherhood - 3 marks

GOOD LUCK

NMTC – BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION JANUARY – FEBRUARY 2012
RM 7 HMDW 071 COMMUNITY MIDWIFERY
TIME ALLOWED: 1½ Hrs
ESSAY

Instructions:

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet
- Each question carries 20 marks.
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers.

Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any marks.

Question One

- a. Differentiate between population size and population structure - 2 marks
- b. Mention three (3) factors that influence or limit population growth - 3 marks
- Describe the effects of high population growth - 15 marks

Question Two

- a. What is total fertility rate? - 2 marks
- b. Mention six (6) causes of high fertility rate - 6 marks
- c. Explain the measures that can be taken to limit fertility rate - 12 marks

Question Three

- a. What is maternal mortality? - 2 marks
- b. Explain six (6) direct, six (6) indirect complications and three (3) contributory factors that cause maternal mortality - 15 marks
- c. State six (6) preventive measures of maternal mortality - 3 marks

INDEX NUMBER.....
HFNMTC – BEREKUM / ST. MARY'S CAMPUS - DROBO
RM12 & 13 END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION-MAY 2017
RMD 225 COMMUNITY MIDWIFERY
TIME ALLOWED: 2 HOURS

Instructions

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet.
- Each question carries 20 marks.
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers.

Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any marks.

Question One

- a. What are the specifications for setting up maternity home - 7 marks
- b. Mention five (5) major disciplines of nurses and midwives council - 5marks
- c. What push factors contribute to migration - 6marks
- d. What is the importance of knowledge of population to the community midwife - 2marks

Question Two

Mrs Addo reports to your ward with her husband. She wants to know the schedule for tetanus toxoid.

- a. What is the schedule for tetanus toxoid - 5marks
- b. What are some of the things to look out for on refrigerator to maintain the cold chain of a vaccine - 6marks
- c. What are the implications of high population growth - 9marks

Question Three

- a. NMC has rules concerning Midwifery practice. Mention any six (6) of such rules to govern midwifery practice - 6 marks
- b. Systematically or diagrammatically trace the cold chain system and simply explain each - 14 marks

Question Four

Home visiting offers the nurse/midwife a wider a scope of services since she is able to use what the clients have to demonstrate to them

- a. Explain five (5) points on planning and preparation for Home visiting - 5 marks
Safe Motherhood is one of the pillars of reducing maternal and neonatal mortality in Ghana
- b. Mention any three(3) components and 3 target groups of safe Motherhood - 3 marks
- c. State and simply explain any three (3) causes of maternal morbidity - 6 marks
- d. State and simply explain any three (3) causes of maternal mortality - 6marks

NMTC – BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION APRIL 2013
RM-8 HMDW 071 COMMUNITY MIDWIFERY
TIME ALLOWED: 1½ Hrs.

Instructions:

- *Answer all questions.*
- *Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet*
- *Each question carries 20 marks.*
- *Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers.*

Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any marks.

Question One

- a. What is migration - 2 marks
- b. State two (2) types of migration - 2 marks
- c. Explain four (4) (each of push and pull factors that influence migration - 16 marks

Question Two

- a. Explain ten (10) responsibilities of a Midwife regarding statistics - 16 marks
- b. State four (4) sources of statistics - 4 marks

Question Three

Ghana is ranked 41st on the World Maternal Mortality rate index with 350 deaths per 100,000 live births (WHO 2008).

- a. Explain ten (10) preventive measures that can be used to reduce the deaths. - 15 marks
- b. Give two (2) importance for studying morbidity and mortality - 3 marks
- c. State the formula for calculating maternal mortality rate - 2 marks

NMTC – BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION JUNE 2014
RM 9, H MDW 071 COMMUNITY MIDWIFERY
TIME ALLOWED: 1 ½ Hrs
ESSAY

Instructions:

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet
- Each question carries 20 marks.
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers.

Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any marks.

Question One

- a. What is fertility? 1 mark
- b. State and explain any **five(5)** causes of high fertility rate 10 marks
- c. Mention the **Six(6)** external causes and **three(3)** internal causes of morbidity 9 marks

Question Two

- a. State and explain **five(5)** activities involved in domiciliary midwifery 15marks
- b. Traditional Birth Attendants (TBAs) are found in some parts of the country.
Vividly explain what they do 5marks

Question Three

- a. List the **three(3)** factors that influence the population growth 3marks
- b. Explain any **one(1)** of the factors indicated in (a) above 8 marks
- c. Mrs. Donkor wants to establish her private maternity home.
List **Nine (9)** things she must do or acquire before she can start operating 9 marks

NMTC - HOLY FAMILY – BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION- DECEMBER, 2015
COMMUNITY MIDWIFERY (RM 11)
TIME: 2HOURS 20MINUTES
ANSWER ALL QUESTIONS (60 MARKS)

Question One

- a) As a community midwife, list the other types of health facilities and service providers you can work with in your operational area. - (8marks)
- b) Define the term Cold Chain. - (4marks)
- c) State and explain the uses of Age-structure in a given population. - (8marks)

Question Two

Home visiting offers the nurse/midwife a wider scope of services since she is able to use what the clients have to demonstrate to them.

- a) Explain six (6) points on Planning and Preparation for Home Visiting. - (6marks)
- b) Define the term population. - (4marks)
- c) The target for Ghana Immunization Programme on Vaccine preventable diseases in children from 0-5 years has been 80%. Explain five (5) immunization strategies in Ghana. - (10marks)

Question Three

- a) Elaborate Tetanus-Toxoid immunization schedule for Women in Fertility Age. - (10marks)
- b) The legal aspect of nursing is an integral part of everyday activities in general health, mental health and midwifery practice. Explain any six (6) behaviors and attitudes of a nurse that may result in a lawsuit. - (6 marks)
- c) State four (4) things to remember in maintaining vaccines' potency. - (4marks)

NMTC - HOLY FAMILY – BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION- DECEMBER, 2015
COMMUNITY MIDWIFERY (RM 11)
TIME: 2HOURS 20MINUTES
ANSWER ALL QUESTIONS (60 MARKS)

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- a. As a community midwife, list the other types of health facilities and service providers you can work with in your operational area. (8marks) -
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Question Three

- a. Elaborate Tetanus-Toxoid immunization schedule for Women in Fertility Age. (10marks) -
- b. The legal aspect of nursing is an integral part of everyday activities in general health, mental health and midwifery practice. Explain any six (6) behaviors and attitudes of a nurse that may result in a lawsuit. (6 marks) -
- c. State four (4) things to remember in maintaining vaccines' potency. (4marks) -

NMTC - HOLY FAMILY – BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION- DECEMBER, 2015
COMMUNITY MIDWIFERY (RM 11)
TIME: 2HOURS 20MINUTES
ANSWER ALL QUESTIONS (60 MARKS)

Question One

- a. As a community midwife, list the other types of health facilities and service providers you can work with in your operational area. - (8marks)
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- a. Elaborate Tetanus-Toxoid immunization schedule for Women in Fertility Age. - (10marks)
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- c. State four (4) things to remember in maintaining vaccines' potency. - (4marks)

NMTC – BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION APRIL 2013
RM-8 HMDW 071 COMMUNITY MIDWIFERY
TIME ALLOWED: 1½ Hrs.

Instructions:

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet
- Each question carries 20 marks.
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers.

Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any marks.

Question One

- a. What is migration - 2 marks
- b. State two (2) types of migration - 2 marks
- c. Explain four (4) (each of push and pull factors that influence migration) - 16 marks

Question Two

- a. Explain ten (10) responsibilities of a Midwife regarding statistics - 16 marks
- b. State four (4) sources of statistics - 4 marks

Question Three

Ghana is ranked 41st on the World Maternal Mortality rate index with 350 deaths per 100,000 live births (WHO 2008).

- a. Explain ten (10) preventive measures that can be used to reduce the deaths. - 15 marks
- b. Give two (2) importance for studying morbidity and mortality - 3 marks
- c. State the formula for calculating maternal mortality rate - 2 marks

NMTC – BEREKUM
END OF FIRST SEMESTER – DECEMBER, 2015
COMMUNITY MIDWIFERY (RM 11)
TIME ALLOWED: 2HRS.
ESSAY

Instructions:

- *Answer all questions*
- *Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet*
- *Each question carries 20marks*
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Question One

- a. As a community midwife, list four (4) types of health facilities or service providers you are likely to work with in your operational area. 4marks.
- b. Define the term Cold Chain, with systematically and diagrammatically flow of cold chain. 11marks
- c. State and explain the uses of Age-structure in a given population. 5marks

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- a. Explain six (6) points on Planning and Preparation for Home Visiting. - 8marks
- b. Define the term population. - 2 marks
- c. The target for Ghana Immunization Programme on Vaccine preventable diseases in children from 0-5 years has been 80%. Explain five (5) immunization strategies in Ghana. - 10marks

Question Three

- a. Elaborate Tetanus-Toxoid immunization schedule for Women in Fertility Age. - 5marks
- b. The legal aspect of nursing is an integral part of everyday activities in general health, mental health and midwifery practice. Explain any six (6) behaviors or attitudes of a nurse that may result in a lawsuit. - 7marks
- c. State eight (8) things to remember in maintaining vaccines' potency. - 8marks

NMTC – BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION JANUARY – FEBRUARY 2012
RM 7 HMDW 071 COMMUNITY MIDWIFERY
TIME ALLOWED: 1½ Hrs
ESSAY

Instructions:

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet
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Question One

- a. Differentiate between population size and population structure - 2 marks
- b. Mention three (3) factors that influence or limit population growth - 3 marks
- c. Describe the effects of high population growth - 15 marks

Question Two

- a. What is total fertility rate? - 2 marks
- b. Mention six (6) causes of high fertility rate - 6 marks
- c. Explain the measures that can be taken to limit fertility rate - 12 marks

Question Three

- a. What is maternal mortality? - 2 marks
- b. Explain six (6) direct, six (6) indirect complications and three (3) contributory factors that cause maternal mortality - 15 marks
- c. State six (6) preventive measures of maternal mortality - 3 marks

NMTC – BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION JUNE 2014
RM 9, H MDW 071 COMMUNITY MIDWIFERY
TIME ALLOWED: 1 ½ Hrs
ESSAY

Instructions:

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet
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Question One

- | | |
|---|----------|
| a. What is fertility? | 1 mark |
| b. State and explain any five(5) causes of high fertility rate | 10 marks |
| c. Mention the Six(6) external causes and three(3) internal causes of morbidity | 9 marks |

Question Two

- | | |
|--|---------|
| a. State and explain five(5) activities involved in domiciliary midwifery | 15marks |
| b. Traditional Birth Attendants (TBAs) are found in some parts of the country.
Vividly explain what they do | 5marks |

Question Three

- | | |
|---|---------|
| a. List the three(3) factors that influence the population growth | 3marks |
| b. Explain any one(1) of the factors indicated in (a) above | 8 marks |
| c. Mrs. Donkor wants to establish her private maternity home.
List Nine (9) things she must do or acquire before she can start operating | 9 marks |

NMTC - HOLY FAMILY – BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION- DECEMBER, 2015
COMMUNITY MIDWIFERY (RM 11)
TIME: 2HOURS 20MINUTES
ANSWER ALL QUESTIONS (60 MARKS)

Question One

- a) As a community midwife, list the other types of health facilities and service providers you can work with in your operational area. - (8marks)
- b) Define the term Cold Chain. - (4marks)
- c) State and explain the uses of Age-structure in a given population. - (8marks)

Question Two

Home visiting offers the nurse/midwife a wider scope of services since she is able to use what the clients have to demonstrate to them.

- a) Explain six (6) points on Planning and Preparation for Home Visiting. - (6marks)
- b) Define the term population. - (4marks)
- c) The target for Ghana Immunization Programme on Vaccine preventable diseases in children from 0-5 years has been 80%. Explain five (5) immunization strategies in Ghana. - (10marks)

Question Three

- a) Elaborate Tetanus-Toxoid immunization schedule for Women in Fertility Age. - (10marks)
- b) The legal aspect of nursing is an integral part of everyday activities in general health, mental health and midwifery practice. Explain any six (6) behaviors and attitudes of a nurse that may result in a lawsuit. -(6 marks)
- c) State four (4) things to remember in maintaining vaccines' potency. - (4marks)